

CORRUPTION-THE KUSHANDAH OF THE NATION

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Abstract: this article covers the concept of corruption, the procedure for conducting an anti-corruption examination of regulatory legal acts, the state of the fight against corruption in Jahan and our country today, the legal basis for the fight against corruption, the interaction of state anti-corruption organizations.

Key words: coorupsia, anti-corruption agency, Ombudsman, anti-corruption examination of regulatory legal acts.

Corruption - is a social legal phenomenon associated with the use of a career position for personal purposes. It is known that this vice harms the political and economic development of any society.

Corruption-weakens the rule of Law, leads to a serious violation of the rights and freedoms of citizens.

At the same time promotes the growth of organized crime, terrorism and other threats directed against human security.

According to the UN and the International Monetary Fund, the world economy is 1.5-2.8 trillion a year due to this disaster. up to the dollar is hurt.

In recent years, in order to end corruption in our country, a number of legislative and legislative acts have been adopted and supplemented by norms that have absorbed the positive aspects of the norms of foreign practice.

In particular, the following regulatory legal acts were adopted in the field of anti-corruption:

- Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the fight against corruption" (№. 419, 03.01.2017);
- Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures to implement the provisions of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the fight against corruption" (PL-№. 2752, 02.02.2017);
- -Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures to further improve the Anti-Corruption System in the Republic of Uzbekistan"(PD-5729, 27.05.2019);
- -Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on additional measures to improve the Anti-Corruption System in the Republic of Uzbekistan"(PD-№. 6013, 29.06.2020);

- Resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the organization of the activities of the Anti-Corruption Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan"(PD. 4761, 29.06.2020).

In 2017, the adoption of the anti-corruption law began a new stage in reducing this vice in our society. With this law, the inevitability of a strict punishment for allowing such disgusting situations as corruption, that is, bribery, abuse of law using a career, acquaintance-cognition, kinship, obstruction of the growth of talented personnel, violation of human rights, reprimand was clearly established.

The main purpose of the president's decree "on measures to further improve the Anti-Corruption System in the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated May 27, 2019 is to further increase the effectiveness of the Anti-Corruption System in our country, create a favorable investment and business environment at the highest level, increase and strengthen the country's positive image in the international arena.

Based on these goals, on June 29, 2020, by the decree of the president "on the organization of the activities of the Anti-Corruption Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan", an anti-corruption agency was created, which is considered a special authorized state body in this area. The main task of this authorized body is the formation and implementation of state policy in the field of preventing and combating corruption, ensuring the joint effective activities of state bodies, media, civil society institutions and other representatives of the non-governmental sector.

According to the results of the study and analysis conducted by the anti-corruption agency, 51 submissions were made to ministries and departments, 170 questionnaires and 7 warnings were sent. Of these:

On appeals of individuals and legal entities: 40 submissions, 84 questionnaires and 6 warnings are included.

According to articles published in the media and studies conducted on the initiative of the agency: 5 submissions and 20 questionnaires were included.

According to the results of the Study: 6 submissions, 66 questionnaires and 1 warning is included.

Based on the above, a total of 21 by the bodies of the prosecutor's office on the surveys of the agency (4 in 2020 and in 2021, 17) criminal cases were initiated.

Law "on amendments and additions to certain legislative acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan" (RU-729, 18.11.2021. with the anti-corruption agency it

was established that employees have the right to enter penal institutions without hindrance, to familiarize themselves with the documents in order to study and analyze the occurrence of corruption offenses.

Although measures are being taken to prevent corruption in our country, there are still cases of officials committing corruption-related crimes in law enforcement practice.

Among the serious reforms carried out in recent times, the fight against corruption has become one of the main tasks for Uzbekistan. Because it is known that corruption is not only the custodian of democracy, but also of any progress in general. Of course, various factors influence the reduction in the level of corruption. One of them is the presence of corrupt norms in the adopted legislation itself and the Prevention of the introduction of such norms into practice.

“Presidential Decree on measures to further improve the examination of regulatory legal acts and their projects against corruption” (PD-5263, 22.10.2021.) accepted.

According to the decision, the procedure for conducting an anti-corruption examination of regulatory legal acts will be introduced. In this:

-the current regulatory legal acts are gradually subjected to a full anti-corruption examination;

-in the development of draft normative legal acts, a questionnaire (checklist) of a sample form for identifying corruption factors is filled out and attached to it in the stages until the adoption of the project;

- projects in which the checklist has not been completed are not subject to legal examination by the justice authorities and are returned to the developer;

- regulatory legal acts and corrupt factors identified in their projects related government bodies

and is determined as one of the main criteria for assessing the activities of its organizations.

Conclusions on the results of the examination are subject to mandatory consideration by the relevant state bodies and organizations.

The activities of employees of the legal service of state bodies and organizations for the examination of regulatory legal acts and their projects against corruption are evaluated every six months at the end. Accordingly, measures are taken to stimulate employees by providing one-time funds in the amount of 100% of their position salaries, or to apply disciplinary sanctions against them.

In order to implement the ongoing reforms in practical life, on February 4, 2020, the representative of the Oliy Majlis for Human Rights (Ombudsman) approved a program of departmental anti-corruption measures to ensure the protection of citizens and mechanisms for reporting corruption were introduced by representatives of legal entities. According to the program of these measures:

- The hotline and virtual lobby of the Ombudsman "1096" are operating;
- the appeals of citizens and representatives of legal entities on corruption and other illegal activities of employees are analyzed and their results are discussed at meetings of the Ethics Commission.

Law on amendments and additions to certain legislative acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan" (RU-729, 18.11.2021.), now relatives of persons reporting corruption offenses will also be under the protection of the state (previously only reported persons are provided).

It is worth noting that the positive aspects of the above Foreign experiences were introduced by the Ministry of Justice in the Ministry system, according to which employees are prohibited from receiving gifts during service trips organized by Citizens, employees of other organizations, including to various places and foreign countries.

